

Supporting Information Text S1: Second screening of selected meta-analyses, PRISMA-diagram and potential bias assessment.

Figure 1: PRISMA-diagram used for the review process. Search term used in the process was: (biodiversity OR agrobiodiversity OR arthropods OR contributions) AND (agriculture OR agroecosystem OR agroecosystems OR farmland OR silvopastoral OR landscape OR forest) AND (agroforestry OR silvopasture OR hedgerows OR hedges OR "scattered trees" OR woody OR "forest grazing" OR "livestock disturbances" OR "food forest" OR "landscape complexity" OR "landscape structure") AND (meta-analysis OR "meta analysis" OR meta-analyses OR "meta analyses" OR "systematic review" OR "meta-synthesis").

During the first screening, title and abstracts were screened to see if they were relevant to this study's key objectives: (1) the study quantitatively synthesized existing literature (i.e., a meta-analysis), (2) the study includes either agroforestry elements or landscape structure effects and (3) the study used one or more biodiversity metrics as response variables. Studies focusing on genetic biodiversity were excluded.

During the second screening, we screened full texts of the suitable studies identified in the title and abstract screening. During this full text screening we excluded studies that (1) failed to consider at least 50% of the underlying articles in ecosystems relevant to the European scope¹ (i.e., temperate, boreal and Mediterranean), (2) failed to compile data for agroforestry elements or landscape structure meta-analytically (e.g., narrative reviews), (3) used non-agroecosystem comparators (e.g., forests) or (4) fell beyond our particular scope of agroforestry systems or landscape contexts. The table below shows the decisions made per study assessed at full text stage (**Text S1: Table 1**).

Further on, we identified meta-analysis quantifying landscape structure mitigation on agri-environmental measure-effects (**Text S1: Table 1**). **Text S1: Table 3** provides an overview of the relevant meta-analyses. We provided references for all meta-analyses below.

¹ We made exceptions for studies that assessed the temperate climate separately, in these cases we could accept studies below 50% studies carried out in temperate ecosystems.

Table 1: Reasons of exclusion at full text stage. Green: retained meta-analyses for our study, Yellow: meta-analyses combining agroecological measures (AEM) and landscape context interactions, without additional focus on landscape structure itself, White: meta-analyses using agroforestry elements with non-agroecosystem comparators, Red: all other meta-analyses that were excluded without any other mentioning.

Reference	Title	Insufficient temperate scope	No data compiling	No agro-ecosystem comparator	Difference in scope
(Rifell et al., 2011)	A meta-analysis of bird and mammal response to short-rotation woody crops			Forest comparator	
(Mupepele et al., 2021)	European agroforestry has no unequivocal effect on biodiversity: a time-cumulative meta-analysis				
(García de León et al., 2021)	Contributions of hedgerows to people: a global meta-analysis				
(Torralba et al., 2016)	Do European agroforestry systems enhance biodiversity and ecosystem services? A meta-analysis				
(Marja et al., 2022)	Increasing landscape complexity enhances species richness of farmland arthropods, agri-environment schemes also abundance – A meta-analysis				
(Batáry et al., 2011)	Landscape-moderated biodiversity effects of agri-environmental management: a meta-analysis				Interaction AEM and landscape structure
(Estrada-Carmona et al., 2022)	Complex agricultural landscapes host more biodiversity than simple ones: A global meta-analysis				
(Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2011)	A meta-analysis of crop pest and natural enemy response to landscape complexity				
(Duarte et al., 2018)	The effects of landscape patterns on ecosystem services: meta-analyses of landscape services				
(Niether et al., 2020)	Cocoa agroforestry systems versus monocultures: a multi-dimensional meta-analysis	Tropical			
(da Silveira Bueno et al., 2021)	Could cattle ranching and soybean cultivation be sustainable? A systematic review and a meta-analysis for the Amazon	Tropical			
(Félix et al., 2018)	Enhancing agroecosystem productivity with woody perennials in semi-arid West Africa. A meta-analysis	Tropical			
(Sánchez et al., 2022)	Landscape complexity and functional groups moderate the effect of diversified farming on biodiversity: A global meta-analysis				Interaction diversified farming and landscape structure (Agroforestry is not evaluated separately)
(Bengtsson et al., 2005)	The effects of organic agriculture on biodiversity and abundance: a meta-analysis				Landscape interaction insufficient
(Coutinho et al., 2018)	The influence of local and landscape scale on single response traits in bees: A meta-analysis				
(Tuck et al., 2014)	Land-use intensity and the effects of organic farming on biodiversity: a hierarchical meta-analysis				Interaction organic farming and landscape structure
(Chaudhary et al., 2016)	Impact of Forest Management on Species Richness: Global Meta-Analysis and Economic Trade-Offs		Agroforestry data mainly from tropical regions		
(Santos et al., 2019)	Can agroforestry systems enhance biodiversity and ecosystem service provision in agricultural landscapes? A meta-analysis for the Brazilian Atlantic Forest		Tropical		
(Plieninger et al., 2014)	The Impact of Land Abandonment on Species Richness and Abundance in the Mediterranean Basin: A Meta-Analysis			Natural regeneration comparator	

(Barzan et al., 2021)	Livestock grazing constrains bird abundance and species richness: A global meta-analysis		<i>Forest comparator</i>
(De Beenhouwer et al., 2013)	A global meta-analysis of the biodiversity and ecosystem service benefits of coffee and cacao agroforestry	<i>Tropical</i>	
(Mokondoko et al., 2022)	Biophysical drivers of yield gaps and ecosystem services across different coffee-based agroforestry management types: A global meta-analysis	<i>Tropical</i>	
(de Lima et al., 2018)	Conservation of grasslands and savannas: A meta-analysis on mammalian responses to anthropogenic disturbance		<i>No specific agroforestry treatment</i>
(Shackelford et al., 2013)	Comparison of pollinators and natural enemies: a meta-analysis of landscape and local effects on abundance and richness in crops		
(Crouzeilles et al., 2021)	Associations between socio-environmental factors and landscape-scale biodiversity recovery in naturally regenerating tropical and subtropical forests	<i>(Sub)Tropical</i>	
(Philpott et al., 2009)	Functional richness and ecosystem services: bird predation on arthropods in tropical agroecosystems	<i>Tropical</i>	
(Poch & Simonetti, 2013)	Ecosystem services in human-dominated landscapes: insectivory in agroforestry systems		<i>The relation between natural enemies and pest species is studied rather than the diversity difference of the groups in agroforestry</i>
(Esquivel et al., 2023)	Patterns of shade plant diversity in four agroforestry systems across Central America: a meta-analysis	<i>Tropical</i>	
(Martin & Raveloaritiana, 2022)	Using land-use history and multiple baselines to determine bird responses to cocoa agroforestry	<i>Tropical</i>	
(Marja et al., 2019)	Effectiveness of agri-environmental management on pollinators is moderated more by ecological contrast than by landscape structure or land-use intensity		<i>Interaction AEM and landscape structure</i>
(Pérez-Sánchez et al., 2023)	Flower strip effectiveness for pollinating insects in agricultural landscapes depends on established contrast in habitat quality: A meta-analysis		<i>Interaction flower strips and landscape structure</i>
(Bohada-Murillo et al., 2020)	The effects of forestry and agroforestry plantations on bird diversity: A global synthesis		<i>Forest comparator</i>
(Bennett et al., 2022)	Impact of cocoa agricultural intensification on bird diversity and community composition	<i>Tropical</i>	
(Lichtenberg et al., 2017)	A global synthesis of the effects of diversified farming systems on arthropod diversity within fields and across agricultural landscapes		<i>Interaction organic farming and in-field plant diversity and landscape structure</i>
(Palacios et al., 2013)	Agroforestry systems as habitat for herpetofauna: is there supporting evidence?	<i>Mainly Tropical</i>	
(Bael et al., 2008)	Birds as predators in tropical agroforestry systems	<i>Tropical</i>	
(Plexida et al., 2018)	Factors affecting biodiversity in agrosylvopastoral ecosystems with in the Mediterranean Basin: A systematic review		<i>No clear difference in agroforestry systems and other ecosystems</i>
(Ratajczak et al., 2012)	Woody encroachment decreases diversity across North American grasslands and savannas		<i>Natural process with no exact relation to agroforestry</i>
(Bernes et al., 2018)	Manipulating ungulate herbivory in temperate and boreal forests: effects on vegetation and invertebrates. A systematic review		<i>Natural forest grazing instead of wood pasture</i>
(Staton et al., 2019)	Evaluating the effects of integrating trees into temperate arable systems on pest control and pollination		

(Griffiths et al., 2019)	Environmental effects of short-rotation woody crops for bioenergy: What is and isn't known	<i>Review only</i>
(Núñez-Regueiro et al., 2021)	Effects of bioenergy on biodiversity arising from land-use change and crop type	<i>Mainly Tropical</i>
(Jezeer et al., 2017)	Shaded Coffee and Cocoa - Double Dividend for Biodiversity and Small-scale Farmers	<i>Tropical</i>
(Batáry et al., 2015)	The role of agri-environment schemes in conservation and environmental management	<i>Lessons learned about AEM</i>
(England et al., 2020)	Trees on farms to support natural capital: An evidence-based review for grazed dairy systems	<i>Mainly Tropical</i>
(Jakobsson et al., 2018)	How does roadside vegetation management affect the diversity of vascular plants and invertebrates? A systematic review	<i>Focus on mowing</i>
(Escobar-Ramírez et al., 2019)	Biological control of the coffee berry borer: Main natural enemies, control success, and landscape influence	<i>Tropical</i>
(Prevedello et al., 2018)	The importance of scattered trees for biodiversity conservation: A global meta-analysis	
(Li & Jiang, 2021)	Responses of forest structure, functions, and biodiversity to livestock disturbances: A global meta-analysis	<i>Forest comparator</i>
(Marja et al., 2024)	Quantifying potential trade-offs and win-wins between arthropod diversity and yield on cropland under agri-environment schemes—A meta-analysis	<i>Interaction AEM and landscape structure</i>
(Visscher et al., 2024)	Agroforestry enhances biological activity, diversity and soil-based ecosystem functions in mountain agroecosystems of Latin America: A meta-analysis	<i>Tropical</i>
(Maas et al., 2013)	Bird and bat predation services in tropical forests and agroforestry landscapes	<i>Tropical</i>
(Koellner & Scholz, 2008)	Assessment of land use impacts on the natural environment	

Next tables will show the final meta-analyses selected.

Table 2: The selected meta-analyses, along with its primary conclusion concerning biodiversity, the assessed species groups and regions and the number of effect sizes per study. (black = overall/soil fauna and microbiota, green = plants, orange = pollinators, blue = natural enemies and red = pest species). The specified species groups were categorized in the most suitable groups. *Only studies used for biodiversity metrics are considered. Letters in parentheses refer to the indexes used in the meta-analysis figures.

Citation	Primary conclusion	Assessed species groups	Region	No. studies
(Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2011)	Natural enemies have a strong positive response to landscape complexity , pest abundance doesn't show a significant response.	Natural enemies, generalists, specialists Pest species	Global	46 (a)
(Coutinho et al., 2018)	The descriptors of structural complexity at the local scale explained more of the richness and abundance of bees than the descriptors at landscape scale .	Bees (social, solitary, aboveground nesting, belowground nesting)	Global	43 (b)
(Duarte et al., 2018)	Landscape complexity differentially influenced functional biodiversity. The percentage of natural areas had an effect on natural enemies, pollination, and disease control, while the percentage of non-crop areas had an effect on and pest response. Landscape aggregation benefitted pollination.	Pollinators Natural enemies Pest species	Global	121 (c)
(Estrada-Carmona et al., 2022)	Increasing landscape complexity through changes in composition, configuration, or heterogeneity significantly and positively affects biodiversity.	Overall, invertebrates Plants, weeds Pollinators Natural enemies, spiders, birds Pest species, weeds	Global	157 (d)
(García de León et al., 2021)	Farmland with hedgerows exhibited higher levels of biodiversity than farmland without and provided similar levels of biodiversity than natural habitat.	Overall, vertebrates, invertebrates Plants	Global	170 (e)
(Koellner & Scholz, 2008)	Land use type has a large impact on biodiversity. Intensive land-uses show the lowest plant species richness while low-intensity agriculture shows the highest species richness.	Plants, mosses Mollusks	Europe	23 (f)
(Marja et al., 2022)	Agri-environment schemes in Europe benefit both abundance and species richness, whereas increasing landscape complexity primarily enhances species richness.	Arthropods	Europe	29 (g)
(Mupepele et al., 2021)	Overall, there was no benefit of agroforestry to biodiversity. Silvopastoral systems showed no difference to forests, pastures or abandoned silvopastures. However, silvoarable systems increased biodiversity compared to cropland by 60%.	Overall, arthropods Birds	Europe	50 (h)
(Prevedello et al., 2018)	Areas with scattered trees support greater levels of biodiversity than open areas and maintain communities that are more similar to those in habitat patches.	Overall, vertebrates, arthropods Plants, woody plants, herbs	Global	62 (i)
(Shackelford et al., 2013)	Compositional complexity at both landscape and local scales had	Arthropods Pollinators, bees	Global	46 (j)

	positive effects on pollinators and natural enemies, but different effects on different taxa.	Beetles, parasitoids, spiders Beetles, parasitoids, spiders			
(Staton et al., 2019)	Natural enemy abundance increased (+24%), arthropod herbivore/pest abundance decreased (-25%) in silvoarable systems significantly.	Natural enemies Pest species	Temperate regions	19	(k)
(Torralba et al., 2016)	Agroforestry promotes biodiversity, stressing the importance of promoting features and practices that act at a landscape scale.	Overall, arthropods Plants Fungi Birds	Europe	53	(l)

Table 3: Meta-analyses in our database relating agro-ecological measures with landscape context, along with its primary conclusion concerning biodiversity, the assessed species groups and regions and the number of effect sizes per study. (black = overall/soil fauna and microbiota, green = plants, orange = pollinators, blue = natural enemies and red = pest species). The specified species groups were categorized in the most suitable functionalities. *Only studies used for biodiversity metrics are considered. Letters in parentheses refer to the indexes used in the meta-analysis figures. (SR = species richness, ab = abundance).

Citation	Primary conclusion	Assessed species groups	Region	No. studies
(Batáry et al., 2011)	Agri-environmental management enhanced species richness and abundance but its effectiveness towards varied with landscape complexity .	Overall, arthropods Plants Pollinators Birds Herbivores	Europe	47 (SR) 46 (ab)
(Marja et al., 2019)	Ecological contrast was most important in determining the effectiveness of agri-ecological management, but landscape structure and regional land-use intensity played an additional role .	Pollinators	Europe	62
(Pérez-Sánchez et al., 2023)	Flower strip effects on pollinators increased in comparison with higher contrasts in habitat quality between the flowers strips and control habitats.	Pollinators	Europe	29 21 (SR) 27 (ab)
(Lichtenberg et al., 2017)	Organic farming and higher in-field plant diversity enhanced arthropod abundance, increasing richness as well. Richness on farms embedded in complex relative to simple landscapes .	Arthropods Pollinators Detritivores Predators Herbivores	Global	235
(Sánchez et al., 2022)	Diversified farming systems have 26% higher species richness than simplified systems, but are highly variable across functional groups and landscape complexity .	Overall Autotrophs Pollinators Decomposers Natural enemies Pests	Global	237
(Tuck et al., 2014)	Biodiversity effects due to organic farming are higher in landscapes with higher land-use intensity .	Overall, Arthropods Plants, Producers Pollinators Decomposers, Microbes Predators, Birds Pests	Global	94
(Marja et al., 2024)	In simple landscapes, agri-environmental schemes support higher biodiversity levels , but implicate yield in the same magnitude. In complex landscapes, both yield and arthropod biodiversity are not affected significantly .	Arthropods Pollinators Natural enemies	Europe	26

We performed basic checks on the case-study overlap within the selected meta-analyses in order to conclude whether they would be compatible or not. In summary, we can conclude that each agroforestry-based meta-analysis adds more than 75% new data (**Fig. 2**) and thus we chose to analyze all of them. One exception has to be made concerning the work of Koellner & Scholz (2008): plant data for hedgerows are implemented there as case-study inside García de León et al. (2021). Therefore, we excluded this part from Koellner & Scholz (2008).

The biasness-assessment of meta-analyses is harder, especially within the ecological field (Romanelli et al. 2021², Woodcock et al. 2014³). For the studies of Torralba et al. (2016), Mupepele et al. (2021) and Prevedello et al. (2018), we retrieved evidence wherein the authors claimed no publication bias was present. There are some methodological differences among the meta-analyses, but all authors are however transparent in the reporting of their methods. For instance, Koellner & Scholz (2008) reanalyzed plot data across several Swiss studies and thus have analyzed a fairly complete dataset across a limited spatial scale. All other studies carried out queries using Web of Science, but Prevedello et al. (2018) checked the cross-references, while other articles screened additional databases (e.g., Torralba et al. (2016)) and/or used a query in an additional language (García de León et al. (2021)). Seen the publishing of all these studies in well-known journals, we decided to not reject any of these studies.

Figure 2: Overlap matrix on agroforestry-based meta-analyses. For this we retrieved all corresponding references being used (i.e., only the biodiversity references for Torralba et al. (2016) and the biodiversity-agroecosystem related for García de León et al. (2021)). The last column indicates the percentage of case-studies used in any other selected meta-analysis.

² Romanelli, J.P., Meli, P., Naves, R.P., Alves, M.C. and Rodrigues, R.R. (2021), Reliability of evidence-review methods in restoration ecology. *Conservation Biology*, 35: 142-154. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.13661>

³ Woodcock, P., Pullin, A. S., & Kaiser, M. J. (2014). Evaluating and improving the reliability of evidence syntheses in conservation and environmental science: A methodology. *Biological Conservation*, 176, 54–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2014.04.020>

In the next step, a second-order meta-analysis is applied. To achieve this, effect sizes need to be converted when needed. **Table 4** gives an overview of the effect sizes handling and relevant metadata. All relevant formulas and components have been added.

Table 4: The effect sizes specifications and data manipulations.

First author	<i>First author of the meta-analysis</i>
Theme	<i>Global topic of the specified effect size (Agroforestry or Landscape structure)</i>
TAG	<i>Type of agroforestry or landscape structure metric</i>
Functional group	<p><i>Each effect size was assigned to the relevant species group(s): Plants, Pollinators, Soil fauna, Natural enemies and Pest species as presented by the meta-analyses. Effect sizes referring to bigger species groups, which are not classifiable in functional groups were added to a group assessing biodiversity overall:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall: overall biodiversity metrics • Autotrophs: plants, moss, lichens • Pollinators: bees, bumblebees, butterflies, flies, hymenoptera, hoverflies • Soil fauna: spiders, mites, springtails, fungi, microbes, bacteria, worms, millipedes, isopods, beetles, nematodes, detritivores, gastropods, harvestmen, myriapods • Natural enemies: spiders, beetles, birds, herpetofauna, harvestmen, parasitoids, bats • Pest species: bugs, gastropods, grasshoppers, weeds, herbivores
Metric	<i>Type of response being used in the analyses: ROM (back-transformed Ratio of Means), LROM (logarithmic Ratio of Means), SMD (Standard Mean Difference), Pearson's R, Hedge's g, Fisher's Z</i>
n	<i>The number of effect sizes summarized for the specific metric</i>
Q_effect / CI	<i>Effect sizes and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were extracted directly from the studies. If no exact values were mentioned in the article, we used https://plotdigitizer.com/app to extract them from reported figures</i>
Effect size homogenization	<p>(Staton et al., 2019): Conversion of ROM to LROM</p> <p>(Torralba et al., 2016): The study reports both LROM metrics as Hedge's g metrics for biodiversity effects. For quantitative analysis we only used the LROM metrics.</p> <p>(Koellner & Scholz, 2008): The study reports mean values for different plot types. We calculated LROM effect sizes for all suitable comparisons (escalc) and then used a meta-analysis technique (rma) to recalculate just one effect size per group</p> <p>(Prevedello et al., 2018): The study reports two suitable effect sizes (ROM) for plants and four separate effect sizes on biodiversity without a uniform one for overall biodiversity. Response ratio means across all effect sizes per group were recalculated according to Hedges et al. (1999) and converted afterwards from ROM to LROM</p> <p>(García de León et al., 2021): The study reports SMD effect sizes which are not convertible into LROM. We calculated LROM effect sizes starting from the publicly available database for biodiversity effects compared to farmland (escalc; we excluded records that had a means of zero for either Treatment (hedgerows) or Control (farmland)) and then used a meta-analysis technique (rma (method = "DL"); where variance was zero, we adjusted to 0.000000000001) to recalculate just one effect size per group</p> <p>(Marja et al., 2022): The study reports compiled Pearson's R effect sizes for both richness and abundance metrics and the full database with Fischer's Z effect sizes. We recalculated the meta-analysis effects using the full database for landscape complexity effects using rma (method = "DL") for all groups identifiable (overall biodiversity, soil fauna, natural enemies and pollinators)</p> <p>(Coutinho et al., 2018): The study report Fisher's Z values for different bee types. Response ratio means across all effect sizes were recalculated according to Hedges et al. (1999).</p> <p>(Estrada-Carmona et al., 2022): Conversion of Pearson's R to Fisher's Z</p>

<p>Formulas for effect size calculation and conversion</p>	$ROM = \frac{\mu_{Exp}}{\mu_{Ctrl}}$ $Var_{ROM} = \frac{n_{Exp} + n_{Ctrl}}{n_{Exp}n_{Ctrl}} \left(\left(\frac{sd_{Exp}}{\mu_{Exp}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{sd_{Ctrl}}{\mu_{Ctrl}} \right)^2 \right)$ $LROM = \ln(ROM)$ $Var_{LROM} = \frac{Var_{ROM}}{ROM^2}$ $z = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{1+r}{1-r} \right)$ $sd = SE\sqrt{n}$ $sd = \frac{\sqrt{n}(CI_{upper} - CI_{lower})}{2 * 1.96}$ $sd = \frac{\sqrt{n}(CI_{upper} - CI_{lower})}{2 * T_{inv}(0.05, N - 1)}$ $Var = sd^2$
<p>Second-order meta-analysis formulas (Hedges et al.,1999)</p>	<p>Inverse variance weights: $w_i = \frac{1}{sd_i^2}$</p> <p>Q-Statistic: $Q = \sum_{i=1}^k w_i \theta_i^2 - \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^k w_i \theta_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i}$</p> <p>Between-study variance: $\sigma^2 = \frac{Q - (k-1)}{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i}}$</p> <p>Random-effects weights: $w_i^* = \frac{1}{sd_i^2 + \sigma^2}$</p> <p>Pooled effect size: $\theta^* = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i^* \theta_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i^*}$</p> <p>Confidence interval: $\theta^* \pm 1.96 \sqrt{\frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i^*}}$ ($k > 5$)</p> <p>Degrees of freedom per study: $df_i = n_i^{Exp} + n_i^{Ctrl} - 2$</p> <p>Confidence interval: $\theta^* \pm 1.96 \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^k w_j^*} \right) \left(1 + 4 \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{1}{df_i} \left(\frac{w_i^*}{w_i} \right)^2 \frac{w_i^* \left(\left(\sum_{j=1}^k w_j^* \right) - w_i^* \right)}{\left(\sum_{j=1}^k w_j^* \right)^2} \right)}$ ($k < 5$)</p>
<p>Components of formulas</p>	<p>$\mu = mean$</p> <p>$n = number\ of\ effect\ sizes\ or\ studies$</p> <p>$sd = standard\ deviation$</p> <p>$SE = standard\ error$</p> <p>$Var = variance$</p>

CI_{upper} = Confidence interval border (high)

CI_{lower} = Confidence interval border (low)

z = Fischer's z effect size

r = Pearson's r correlation coefficient

k = number of metaanalyses

Exp = experiment or treatment

$Crtl$ = control for the experiment

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